

Shifting Defect Self-Regulation via Disordered Vacancies in Hollow Tin Perovskites

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Abstract

Tin(II)-based hybrid halide perovskites typically suffer from severe self-doping behavior as the result of facile oxidation of Sn(II) to Sn(IV), leading to high carrier densities (holes) and metallic-like conductivities that limit their applications. In this contribution, we describe how substituting the large ethylenediammonium cation for methylammonium in the intentionally defective “hollow” perovskite family, $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ (MA = methylammonium, en = ethylenediammonium), where $0 \leq x \leq 0.38$, effectively neutralizes the intrinsic self-doping behavior. The use of a solvent-free, mechanochemical, synthesis route further circumvents oxidative side reactions typical in solution processing, enabling more precise control and

understanding of both composition and defect chemistry. Dark and time-resolved microwave conductivity measurements of these materials as a function of “ x ” reveal two regimes of conductivity suppression: at low x incorporation ($x \leq 0.15$) the carrier density decreases sharply via defect-mediated charge compensation, while higher substitution ($0.15 < x \leq 0.38$) greatly reduces the carrier mobility. At these lower substitution levels, the observations suggest that intrinsic, equilibrium tin vacancies are compensated instead by ionic defects in lieu of mobile holes. For the higher substitution levels, the less mobile carriers exhibit long recombination lifetimes, consistent with polaron-mediated transport. These findings establish a new strategy for relatively low iodine chemical potential synthesis and defect-driven control of carrier concentration in tin halide perovskites, advancing the rational discovery of dopable hybrid semiconductors.

Introduction

Hybrid organic-inorganic perovskites offer uniquely tunable structure-property relationships with applications in radiation detection,¹ computing and thermoelectrics,^{2,3} optics and diodes,⁴ and most notably, photovoltaics (PV).⁵⁻⁷ Leading PV candidate materials primarily employ Pb(II)-based hybrid perovskites. Materials made with Sn(II) instead of Pb(II) offer lower toxicity and comparable *predicted* optoelectronic properties.⁸⁻¹² In practice, though, Sn(II)-based halide perovskites typically suffer from metallic-like intrinsic carrier concentrations as the result of facile oxidation of Sn(II) to Sn(IV), additionally resulting in tin vacancies.⁸⁻¹⁷ Furthermore, bulk Sn(II)-based hybrid halide perovskites are traditionally synthesized using highly acidic solution precipitation susceptible to complex solution equilibria, further complicated by the light or oxygen based degradation of HI(aq).¹⁸ While introduction of SnF₂ in solution helps to mitigate this effect via the anion exchange and preferential solubilization of Sn(IV) by fluorine,¹⁹⁻²¹ the electronic properties remain sensitive to the solution processing conditions.

A class of materials known as 3D “hollow” hybrid halide perovskites are especially interesting as a platform for understanding how crystal chemistry influences defects and doping. In these materials there are two organic cations substituting on the nominally same crystallographic site: a smaller, monovalent cation (e.g. methylammonium, formamidinium) and a larger, often divalent, cation (e.g. ethylenediammonium, hydroxyethylammonium),^{11,22–30} as cartooned in Figure 1. Although cations of these larger sizes typically reduce the dimensionality of hybrid perovskites (e.g. Ruddlesden-Popper and Dion-Jacobson type), here the materials retain the 3D connectivity. The larger cation is compensated, in size and charge, by the generation of tin and iodine vacancies. These Sn(II) vacancies are compensated *ionically* as opposed to *electronically*, which we hypothesized might help reduce, and control, high intrinsic carrier concentrations that typically arise from adventitious Sn(II) vacancies that naturally compensate holes that arise from adventitious oxidation.^{9,10,23,31} Thus, vacancy generation via organic cation substitution offers a level of defect control that other hybrid perovskites do not offer, making these hollow structures ideal candidates for understanding how intrinsic defects can affect the electronic properties.

Nearly all synthetic methods to produce tin-iodide materials require a high iodine chemical potential, thus preventing understanding of crystal chemical effects without direct coupling to iodine equilibria. Solution synthesis of 3D “hollow” hybrid halide perovskites yields materials with stoichiometric ratios distinct from the nominal solution ratios.^{27,30,33,34} This reflects a dynamic equilibrium dictating precipitation,³⁵ thus obfuscating how to synthetically control carrier concentration, particularly in the limit of extreme iodine excess. As the preparation method of hybrid perovskites plays a crucial role in the product formation, mechanochemical synthesis has emerged as an advantageous solvent-free synthesis alternative with reproducible results.^{33,36–42} Here, solvents are avoided opting instead for a solid-state procedure that reduces the chances of unintended equilibria impacting the family of products.

Figure 1: A cartoon visualization of how the crystal structure in the family $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ $0.00 \leq x \leq 0.38$ must propagate increasing amounts of Sn (green atoms) and I (purple atoms) vacancies in order to accommodate the larger size of ethylenediammonium (black carbon atoms), as compared to methylammonium (brown carbon atoms).³²

In this study we discover how intentional introduction of ionic defects modulates the electronic carrier concentration. Discovery of a solvent-free mechanochemical synthesis method yields ideal synthesis of the 3D “hollow” perovskite family, $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ (MA = methylammonium, en = ethylenediammonium) where $0.00 \leq x \leq 0.38$. A combination of powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (^1H NMR) reveal the structure and retention of the nominal synthesis stoichiometry. Optical bandgaps were measured from powdered samples using UV-Visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-DRS). Densitometry data collected for powder samples validate the introduction of a significant concentration of vacancies in line with previous studies. The evolution of electronic properties (conductivity, mobility, lifetime, and carrier density) with chemical substitution is afforded by dark microwave conductivity (DMC) and time-resolved microwave conductivity (TRMC) experiments. Incorporating ethylenediammonium systematically decreases the intrinsic electronic conductivity from

large, metallic values of ≥ 100 S/m ($x = 0.00$) to a more reasonable range for PV applications of 0.5 S/m ($x = 0.38$). This dramatic reduction in conductivity occurs in two regimes. First, for low x incorporation the carrier density drops precipitously, consistent with our hypothesis that the intentional introduction of *ionically* compensated tin vacancies effectively neutralize *electronic* defects. Thereafter, for high x incorporation, the electronic mobility suffers from the high overall defect concentration. This neat synthetic pathway outlines a new way to obtain bulk, highly crystalline, phase-pure, 3D “hollow” hybrid halide perovskites while highlighting the role that crystal chemistry enables the intentional control of carrier concentrations in these “undopable” materials.

Experimental Methods

Starting Materials

Ethylenediamine (99%, Alfa Aesar), iodine (>99.8%, Sigma Aldrich), tin (99% granular 20 mesh, J.T. Baker Chemical Co.), stannous chloride (99%, Fischer Chemical), hydroiodic acid (stabilized with H_3PO_2 , 57% in H_2O , Sigma Aldrich), hypophosphorous acid solution (50 wt% in H_2O , Sigma Aldrich), and methylamine solution (33 wt% in abs. ethanol, Sigma Aldrich) were purchased from stated commercial suppliers and used without further purification.

Synthesis of Precursors

Methylammonium Iodide (MAI)

Aqueous hydroiodic acid (57% w/w in H_2O , 12 mL) and methylamine solution (33 wt% in absolute ethanol, 24 mL) were reacted and stirred in a 0 °C ice bath for 2 hrs. The solution was removed from the ice bath and subsequently stirred at 60 °C until the solution had evaporated yielding the white crystalline methylammonium iodide solid. The resulting

solid was then washed with diethyl ether six times (40 mL/wash) via centrifugation and placed into a vacuum oven overnight at 60 °C. This is an adapted procedure from the reported reference.⁴³ The white methylammonium iodide powder was finely ground for PXRD analysis to be confirmed pure.

Ethylenediammonium Diiodide (enI₂)

Aqueous hydroiodic acid (57% w/w in H₂O, 12 mL) and ethylenediamine solution (2.40 mL) were reacted at room temperature with an immediate precipitation of the white enI₂ solid. The resulting solid was then washed with diethyl ether 10 times (40 mL/wash) via centrifugation and placed into a vacuum oven overnight at 60 °C. The fine, off-white enI₂ powder was finely ground for PXRD analysis to be confirmed pure.

Tin (IV) Iodide (SnI₄)

Using a 2:1 stoichiometric ratio, solid iodine (4.052 g, 15.96 mmol) was ground into a uniform, fine powder using an agate mortar and pestle and mixed with granular (20 mesh) tin (0.9477 g, 7.983 mmol). The resulting mixture was added to a quartz tube. The tube was then briefly evacuated (<30 sec to negate iodine sublimation), flame sealed under static vacuum (~50 mTorr), and placed into a muffle furnace. The temperature was set to 200 °C for 60 hrs at a heating ramp rate of 20 °C/min followed by furnace cooling to room temperature. The resulting bright orange powder was finely ground for PXRD analysis to be confirmed pure. This procedure is reported in previously published work.⁴⁴

Tin (II) Iodide (SnI₂)

Using a 1:1 stoichiometric ratio, tin(IV) iodide (2.52 g, 4 mmol) and granular (20 mesh) tin (0.478 g, 4 mmol) were mixed together in a mortar and pestle. Making sure the two solids are nominally homogenized by mixing, the resulting mixture was added to a quartz tube. The tube was then briefly evacuated (<30 sec to negate iodine sublimation), flame-

sealed under the static vacuum (~ 50 mTorr), and placed into was placed into a muffle furnace. The temperature was set to 600 °C for 32 hrs at a ramp rate of 1.67 °C/min followed by furnace cooling to room temperature. The resulting bright orange-red, air-sensitive powder was finely ground, in an inert atmosphere (glovebox), for PXRD analysis to be confirmed pure. This procedure is reported in previously published work.⁴⁴

Mechanochemical Synthesis of $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$

All sample manipulations during the synthesis of $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ where A-site % $x = 0.00, 0.06, 0.10, 0.15, 0.25, 0.30, 0.34,$ and 0.38 were performed in inert atmospheres. These samples were prepared mechanochemically. In order to target the literature formula materials, $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$, salt precursors were stoichiometrically reacted in a ball-mill with a 3 g batch product targeted. The values noted in the following procedure correspond to the $x = 0.25$ constituent. First, methylammonium iodide (0.7075 g, 4.5 mmol) and ethylenediammonium diiodide (0.4690 g, 1.5 mmol) were added to a zirconia, 20 mL ball mill chamber with 3 large zirconia mixing balls. The chamber was sealed in an inert argon atmosphere and loaded into a Retsch CryoMill (though running at ambient temperature) for a 30 minute, 30 Hz milling schedule. The chamber was brought back into an inert argon atmosphere where the tin iodide (1.8238 g, 4.9 mmol) was added to the organic mixture. The chamber was sealed and once again loaded into the ball mill for a second 90 minute, 30 Hz mill with all constituents. The chamber was once again brought into an inert argon atmosphere where the now black powder was harvested and pelletized (0.25" diameter pellets). The pellets were added to a quartz ampule that was subsequently flame-sealed under vacuum (<60 mTorr) and placed into a convection oven to anneal at 200°C . For samples with $x < 0.30$ an 18 hour anneal was sufficient to equilibrate and fully incorporate the ethylenediammonium diiodide salt. For samples with $x > 0.30$, a 36 hour anneal time was required to fully incorporate the ethylenediammonium diiodide. After annealing, samples were transferred to an argon atmosphere and finely ground for PXRD

analysis to be confirmed phase pure, amongst other characterization. Powders where $x < 0.30$ were black in coloration while $x > 0.30$ were a dark red-black hue.

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD)

All samples were prepared on a off-axis cut zero diffraction silicon wafer. In order to extract an accurate lattice parameter, the XRD specimens were intimately mixed with silicon powder (1-5 mg) as an internal standard for calibrating the sample height. Measurements were completed using a Bruker D8 DaVinci Powder X-ray Diffractometer with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation and a Lynxeye XE-T position-sensitive detector. Quantitative analysis of X-ray diffraction data was performed using the Rietveld method with TOPAS v6 software package to extract unit cell information. As the Bragg reflections broadened beyond the resolution of the instrument, the Lorentzian linewidth was used to estimate the crystalline microstrain during the Rietveld refinement in TOPAS v6.

UV-Visible Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (UV-DRS)

Diffuse reflectance optical spectroscopy measurements were conducted using an Ocean Optics tungsten-halogen light source (Mikropack HL-2000) and an Ocean Insight Flame Miniature Spectrometer 500 (Flame-S-VIS-NIR) equipped with an integrating sphere. A fiber-optic cable was used to illuminate the flat base of a borosilicate glass vial filled with loose powder of the reaction products. A vial containing BaSO_4 was used as a white reflectance standard. The Kubelka–Munk transform was calculated using the formula $(k/s) = ((1 - R_\infty)^2)/(2R_\infty)$, where k is the absorption coefficient, s is the scattering coefficient, and R_∞ is the diffuse reflectance. Optical band gaps are estimated from a plot of $(k/s)^2$ (e.g., Tauc analysis assuming a direct gap between parabolic bands), and then by taking the tangent line of maximal slope at the absorption edge and extrapolating to the $(k/s)^2 = 0$. For MASnI_3 , the band gap was unable to be extrapolated as it resided

outside of the detectable region of the Si-based detector.

Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (^1H NMR)

^1H NMR data was collected on a 400 MHz Bruker NEO400. Roughly ≈ 10 mg of each compound dissolved in deuterated dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO-d_6). Samples for NMR were prepared in an argon-filled glovebox and sealed with rubber septa.

Helium Pycnometry

Experimental determination of the density was evaluated using a Micrometrics Accupyc II 1340 helium pycnometer equipped with 0.1 and 1.0 cm^3 aluminum sample chamber sizes. Between 500-600 mg of sample (to the nearest 0.0001 g) was placed into the 1.0 cm^3 sample cup and sample volume determination was performed based on He displacement. Each sample was measured 10 times and the sample volume with standard deviation was recorded. The average volume for each sample was used for the respective density calculation. Samples were not retained in a rigorously air-free environment but were transferred to the He-filled chamber in less than 2 minutes of air exposure.

Dark and Time Resolved Microwave Conductivity

Dark microwave conductivity (DMC) measurements were conducted as previously described,⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸ with the modification that a new experimental setup was constructed and employed at Colorado State University (CSU) to accelerate the synthesis and measurement cycle. This new system operates as a turn-key instrument for measuring the equilibrium conductivity/dielectric constant of powder samples enclosed in either EPR tubes, bulk borosilicate tubes, or in the present case, borosilicate capillaries (1.2 x 1.4 mm IDxOD). For these experiments, samples contained in flame sealed, evacuated capillaries, transferred directly from an argon-filled glovebox to the vacuum line without air exposure.

A Python-based graphical user interface integrates both data acquisition and analysis using built-in lookup tables of electromagnetic simulation data that calibrate the complex conductivity (permittivity) for each kind of tube, using methods previously described.⁴⁵ Full details are included in the Supporting Information, along with a block diagram of the complete instrument (Figure S11).

Time-resolved microwave conductivity (TRMC) measurements were conducted on established equipment⁴⁵ with the exception that a high repetition-rate low pulse energy laser (CryLas GmbH FTSS355-Q2, 355 nm, 10 kHz, 3 μ J / pulse, 1.1 ns FWHM; 2×10^{12} photons/cm²/pulse delivered uniformly across the samples projected area) was used to excite the sample, and data were recorded on a Tektronix MSO44B oscilloscope that is capable of averaging at the full repetition rate of the laser. An average of approx. 0.5M to 5M pulses were collected for each sample depending on signal strength.

The photoconductivity amplitude was calibrated as previously described,^{45,47} using simulations conducted specifically for the capillary tubes used in this work. Capillary tubes with a small ID were important, because the powder conductivities for many of the material compositions reported here would have been outside the instruments dynamic range if larger tubes with more material were used. A unique sensitivity factor was calculated for each sample to account for the widely varying equilibrium conductivity and permittivity of these samples.

Photoconductivity signals are expressed as the product of charge carrier yield (ϕ) and the sum of the electron and hole mobilities ($\Sigma\mu$). Each transient is fit using a well-characterized instrument response function (exponentially modified gaussian) convolved with one or two term multi-exponential function.^{49,50} The values shown in Figure 5(b) are obtained by summing up all the exponential prefactors, allowing us to resolve the magnitude of the yield mobility product even when the carrier lifetime is less than 10x smaller than the nominal width of the instrument response function.

Results and Discussion

The compounds, $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$, where $\text{MA} = \text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3^+$ and $\text{en} = \text{NH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_3^{2+}$ were successfully prepared in bulk using a solvent-free, mechanochemical method for the nominal values, $x = 0.00, 0.06, 0.10, 0.15, 0.25, 0.30, 0.34,$ and 0.38 . Reactions targeting a previously reported product formula³⁰ followed the balanced chemical reaction between simple salts,

yielding nominally phase-pure cubic perovskites after understanding aspects of the synthesis process (Figure 1). Ball-milling of the three salts all at once yields primarily MASnI_3 , as inferred from the lattice parameter ($a = 6.24 \text{ \AA}$) and residual enI_2 , as observed from PXRD (Figure 2(a)). Using two milling steps, 30 minutes of $\text{MAI} + \text{enI}_2$, followed by the addition of the SnI_2 for another 90 minute total mill, yields a product with a shifted lattice parameter ($a = 6.27 \text{ \AA}$) but broad diffraction peaks and residual salt impurities as observed by PXRD. The increased lattice parameter suggests that pre-mixing the organic cations yields better incorporation of the ethylenediammonium cation into the perovskite structure, as consistent from a solution-phase precipitation synthesis.³⁰ Post-ball milling pelletization and annealing yields homogeneous, cubic perovskites. From samples annealed at different temperatures (100 °C, 150 °C, and 200 °C; higher temperatures yield decomposition), the PXRD patterns reveal a much sharper, shifted set of peaks (Figure 2(c)-(e)). The highest temperature, 200 °C, yields the sharpest diffraction peaks and a lattice parameter consistent with a prior study.³⁰

As expected, the ratio of organic cations (methylammonium to ethylenediammonium) input into the synthesis reaction follows through to the final crystalline products, as determined by quantitative ^1H NMR spectroscopy. Dissolution of the perovskites in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ permits differentiation and quantification of the two cations by ^1H NMR spectroscopy

Figure 2: A portion of the raw PXRD patterns of the resulting products from stoichiometric reactions targeting $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ $x = 0.25$ where (a) all salts were milled together, (b) the organic salts were milled first together and then further milled after with the inorganic salt, and where an organic and total mill were completed followed by an annealing step at (c) 100°C , (d) 150°C , and (e) 200°C . A focused section of these plots (right column) highlights the peak shift and shape changes with different processing methods. The asterisks highlight impurity phase peaks seen in initial attempts.

(Figure S1- S8).³⁰ Using the methyl ($-\text{CH}_3$) or ammonium ($-\text{NH}_3^+$) groups present in the methylammonium (MA) cation or the methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) and ammonium ($-\text{NH}_3^+$) groups present in ethylenediammonium, peak integration of either aprotic or protic groups validate the targeted x values: $x = 0.00, 0.06, 0.10, 0.15, 0.25, 0.30, 0.34, 0.38$ for $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$.

From PXRD, $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ crystallizes as a cubic perovskite with a linearly increasing unit cell volume with x . The compounds are isostructural to $\alpha\text{-MASnI}_3$ ($Pm\bar{3}m$ space group) but show a systematic increase in unit cell dimensions with increasing x (Figure 3(a)). This manifests as a linear increase in the unit cell volume obtained from quantitative phase analysis using the Rietveld method (Figure 3 (b)); full patterns with fits shown in Figure S10). This expansion is consistent with insertion of a larger organic cation and/or increased Sn and I vacancy concentrations and the resulting decreased electrostatic attractions.³⁰ While some microstrain is expected from the creation of significant vacancy

content, the microstrain extracted from quantitative phase analysis of the PXRD does not depend on x (Figure 3(c)). Together, this suggests solid-solution-like behavior with increasing ethylenediammonium content and the formation of homogeneous crystals through the solvent-free, mechanochemical synthesis after annealing.

Figure 3: Selected region of the analyzed PXRD patterns of $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ where $0 \leq x \leq 0.38$ highlighting a) the shift to lower 2θ as (b) the unit cell increases in size when more en is incorporated. (c) The incorporation of ethylenediammonium does not influence the PXRD-derived microstrain.

Measurement of the optical absorption confirms the reported visible light absorption and expected bandgap shift expected across the values of x incorporation. UV-Visible diffuse reflectance spectra of powder samples exhibit onsets of light absorption. Fitted tangent lines to the pseudo-absorbance for a direct bandgap ($(k/s)^2$) extrapolated to zero absorbance are interpreted as the optical bandgap (Figure 4(a)). The MASnI_3 sample's bandgap was below that of our detector's limit. The trend in band gaps shift qualitatively compares well with the previously reported trend.³⁰ The presence of tailing below the extrapolated band gaps suggests the presence of optically detectable defect states,⁵¹⁻⁵³ as might be expected from the presence of significant vacancy defects. The bandgap of these

Figure 4: (a) Diffuse reflectance spectra shown as $(k/s)^2$ collected from $MA_{1-x}en_xSn_{1-0.7x}I_{3-0.4x}$. (b) The extracted optical bandgap values highlights show the linear increases in optical gap energy with incorporated fraction of ethylenediammonium. Literature values shown for comparison as open squares.³⁰ (c) Experimental densities show the expected trend from the chemical formula, also in agreement with a prior study (open squares).³⁰

materials increases as a function of x , as attributed to the decrease in orbital overlap for the atoms primarily responsible for the electronic band structure, Sn and I,³⁰ due to their vacancies.

The heavy atom Sn and I vacancies generated to accommodate the ethylenediammonium subsequently reduce the bulk density of the material. Experimental measurement of the bulk density using helium pycnometry reveals a decreasing density with increasing x , decreasing from 3.60 g cm^{-3} ($x = 0.00$) to 3.27 g cm^{-3} ($x = 0.38$) (Figure 4(c)), agreeing with literature precedent.³⁰ Here, while the trend is monotonic, it is not linear and plateaus at two values of reduced density (≈ 3.4 and 3.27 g cm^{-3}), suggesting of two regimes of vacancy incorporation, as discussed later. The density is consistently lower than a theoretical calculation (solid line, Figure 4(c)) using the assumed formula weight from

$\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ normalized by a linear expression for the unit cell volume with x (solid line, Figure 3(b)).

Figure 5: Analysis of DMC and TRMC measurements showing the (a) the dark conductivity (σ_{dark}), (b) yield mobility product ($\phi\Sigma\mu$), (c) average lifetime of charge carriers ($\langle\tau\rangle$), and (d) the calculated carrier density (n) as a function of ethylenediammonium incorporation across $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$. Included on (a, d) are the approximated minimum-bound to the conductivity and carrier density for MASnI_3 along with a range of literature-reported carrier densities.^{52,54–57}

We employ dark and time resolved microwave conductivity experiments (DMC, TRMC) to assess the impact of composition on equilibrium conductivity, carrier mobility, photoexcited carrier lifetime, and carrier density. Across all compositions, the equilibrium conductivity decreases with substitution (Figure 5(a)). This trend was also reported but to a lesser extent in the lead-base congener, $(\text{MA})_{1-x}(\text{en})_x(\text{Pb})_{1-0.7x}(\text{I})_{3-0.4x}$.⁵⁸ Here, we assign changes in conductivity to both changes in the mobility and the carrier density. Mobility is obtained from TRMC measurements (assuming $\Phi = 1$) which then allows us to calculate the carrier density from the equilibrium conductivity via $\sigma = en\mu$. Together, these reveal two compositional regimes of electronic behavior: (i) $x \leq 0.15$ yields a

reduction in carrier density with little change in mobility; (ii) $x > 0.15$ exhibits a fast decline in mobility, longer photogenerated carrier lifetimes, and ultimately an apparent increase in calculated carrier density (Figure 5). While the relative dielectric permittivity also follows these trends, it remains high (≈ 20) even at $x = 0.38$ (Figure S12). For MASnI_3 the microwave power reflectance revealed a conductivity higher than what can be quantified using the microwave-based measurement in our present configuration ($\sigma \approx 100 \text{ S/m}$) (Figures S15-S20). As such, we present the metallic-like minimum bound to the conductivity, which agrees well with literature values measured on optimized thin films and single crystals.^{55,56,59-61}

For low x , the substitution is most consistent with shifting the defect equilibria governing charge carriers. Increasing x from 0.06 to 0.15 yields only a ≈ 2 -fold decrease in mobility ($1.24 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $0.65 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Across the same compositional trend, the carrier lifetime increases slightly from 4.24 ns ($x = 0.06$) to 5.47 ns at ($x = 0.15$). This may be attributed to reduced pseudo first-order recombination from reduction in the dark carrier concentration. The most significant finding is the rapid decrease in carrier density from over $5.02 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ ($x = 0.00$, estimated minimum using neighboring member mobility) to $4.69 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ ($x = 0.15$).

We hypothesize that this drop in carrier density is attributable to a shift in the intrinsic defect equilibria. Computational studies uniformly agree that tin vacancies are the primary compensating defect for the uncontrolled hole doping (i.e., Sn(II) to Sn(IV) oxidation) in tin halide-based perovskites,^{9,16,17,20,21,62-66}

Introduction of ethylenediammonium into MASnI_3 primarily yields the equilibrium,

The coupling of these equilibria yields the net effect:

The nature of ethylenediammonium incorporation also lends itself to having less available Sn(II) sites in the final structure further reducing the opportunity for Sn(II) to unfavorably oxidize to Sn(IV) and generate holes. This therefore helps to explain why the incorporation of small diammonium cations improves the open-circuit voltage in photovoltaic devices.^{23,24,26} Previous work on the Pb(II)-based congeners with ethylenediammonium substitution has also alluded to the fact that small changes in preparation conditions can lead to variations in defects and overall structure influencing conductivity drastically.^{58,67} This crystal-chemical approach is thus less sensitive to the synthesis and processing conditions (e.g., HI decomposition¹⁸ or SnF₂ use¹⁹⁻²¹).

For substitution beyond $x = 0.15$, the conductivity continues to decrease but primarily due to a precipitous drop in carrier mobility. The extremely low mobility could arise from the extreme disruption of electronic bandwidth,³⁰ defect scattering, or polaron localization. With the highly deformable Sn-I substructure, introducing a significant fraction of vacancies permits relaxation of the structure around local charge imbalances. The large increase in carrier lifetime from $x = 0.15$ to $x = 0.25$ (5.47 ns to 281 ns) further supports the notion of charge localization. With the increasing band gap upon substitution (Figure 4), formerly shallow acceptor states may move deeper into the gap thus promoting localization. Meanwhile, the inferred carrier density inflects and increases for $x > 0.15$. This could reflect a change in the dominant defect equilibria. However, it is important to note the possibility that *dielectric* loss plays a role in the higher x samples, as dielectric loss is indistinguishable from conductivity.⁴⁵ If structural distortions available only at high substitution levels allow for more dipolar relaxation and phonon scattering, their relative microwave absorption can increase leading to higher dielectric loss.

Conclusion

Together, these findings indicate how ethylenediammonium substitution influences the intrinsic defect equilibria and its impact on the the electronic conductivity, mobility, and carrier density. Discovery of a neat (solvent free), mechanochemical synthesis approach permits the synthesis of “hollow” $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{en}_x\text{Sn}_{1-0.7x}\text{I}_{3-0.4x}$ without complicating factors related to the solution equilibria (e.g., HI decomposition) and in conditions with a lower iodine chemical potential.¹⁸ Furthermore, the powders produced via this method are crystallographically and electronically homogeneous. Substitution with ethylenediammonium manifests in two regimes of influence over the electronic properties. For $x \leq 0.15$, the electronic properties resemble that of MASnI_3 with a shifted intrinsic defect equilibria resulting in significantly less *p*-type self-doping. For $x > 0.15$, the behavior resembles that of a distinct, highly defective material with more polaronic behavior with low carrier mobilities but long excited-state carrier lifetimes. Thus, the introduction of small amounts of vacancy-promoting organic cations uses crystal chemistry to neutralize the high intrinsic carrier concentration and resulting conductivity that have limited the utility of materials such as MASnI_3 .

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